

Development of Bio-based Flame Retardants using Recovered Biopolymers from Wastewater Sludge

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CONTENT

Background

Experimental

Results and Discussion

Conclusions

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➤ Natural fibre based flame retardants

Feather

Fighting fires with feathers - chicken waste gets a new use as fire-retardant

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(D. Jung, D. Bhattacharyya, ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng (2019) 7(23) 19072)

➤ Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS)

Wastewater treatment plants

Waste sludge

EPS extraction

EPS

➤ Potential Applications of EPS

- Paper coating
- Flame retardant
- Cement curing

Combustion Cycle / Flame Retardation

(Mouritz, 2006)

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EPS Extraction and Phosphorylation

➤ EPS Extraction

EPS extraction process diagram using centrifugal force

➤ Phosphorylation process

EPS / STMP

EPS coated Wool Felt

➤ Wool felt

- Medium density (250 kg/m^3) wool felt for filtration, cladding and sealing applications

➤ Vacuum-assisted Dip Coating Method

- **Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy**
- **Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)**
- **Vertical burn test (ASTM D3801)**
- **Cone calorimeter**
- **Scanning electron microscope (SEM)**

- **ASTM E1354 standard**
- **50 kW/m² heat flux**
- **Fire reaction properties**
 - Time to ignition (TTI)
 - Peak heat release rate (PHRR)
 - Total heat release (THR)
 - Total smoke production (TSP)

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Extracellular polymeric substance (EPS)

Trisodium trimetaphosphate (STMP)

STMP treated EPS

- 1072 cm^{-1} and 1233 cm^{-1} : Polysaccharide
- The new peak at 998.7 cm^{-1} indicates that the P-OH group has successfully bonded with EPS.
- The new peak at 1286.44 cm^{-1} indicates that the EPS has got P=O stretching vibration because of adding STMP.

Thermogravimetric Analysis

Sample	Amount of residue at 800 °C (wt%)
EPS from wastewater sludge	27.4
1.5 wt% STMP treated EPS	30.7
3 wt% STMP treated EPS	41.1
Wool	24.1
Ammonium polyphosphate	29

Fire Reaction Properties

➤ Heat release rate

Sample	CO yield (kg/kg)	CO ₂ yield (kg/kg)
Wool felt	0.0108	1.21
3 wt% EPS wool felt	0.0151	1.33
3 wt% EPS/1.5 wt% STMP wool felt	0.0155	1.3
3 wt% EPS/2 wt% STMP wool felt	0.0159	1.24
3 wt% EPS/3 wt% STMP wool felt	0.0109	1.08

Microstructures of Char

Wool felt

Wool/EPS felt

Wool/EPS/STMP felt

Vertical Burn

Wool felt

**EPS coated
Wool felt**

**EPS/STMP1.5
coated Wool
felt**

**EPS/STMP2
coated Wool
felt**

**EPS/STMP3
coated Wool
felt**

EPS coated Flax Fibre/PP Composites

Untreated Flax

EPS coated Flax

Flax

EPS solution

EPS coated flax fibres

~ 5 wt.% EPS absorbed in flax

Granulator

Short fibres after grinding

Melt-blending (compounding)

Composite pellets

Compression moulding process

EPS coated flax fibre (30 wt.%) based composite panels

Thermogravimetric Analysis

➤ EPS coated flax fibres

➤ EPS coated flax fibres/PP composite

Fire Reaction Properties

	PP	EPS	EPS coated flax/PP
Peak heat release rate (kW/m ²)	1054	163.2	697.3
Total heat release (MJ/m ²)	117	8.8	71.4
CO (kg/kg)	0.029	0.036	0.032
CO ₂ (kg/kg)	2.93	1.21	2.28

- The phosphorylation process of EPS created additional phosphorus groups and improved char forming capability of the biopolymer
- The ~ 30 wt% EPS in wool felt achieved the self-extinguishment and reduced peak heat release rate (~18 %) compared to one of wool felt.
- The addition of EPS and STMP into wool felt achieved the remarkable decrease in peak heat release rate (35 %) in comparison with one of wool due to the compact char formation.
- The 30 wt.% EPS coated flax fibre/PP composite achieved the reduction of peak heat release rate (33.8 %) and CO production rate (55.7 %) in comparison with those of PP.
- EPS contributed effective char formation to reduce flammability of wool felt and composite.

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THANK YOU

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